

CURRENT ISSUES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF FOREIGN SPEECH STUDENT ACTIVITIES

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شىنجاڭ پىداگوگىكا ئۇنىۋېرسىتېتى

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Annotation: *This article describes most used reading materials with specialized texts. The intention of this research is to inspire a discussion about the changes in reading aspects with the revolution in communication and representation forms as a result of digitalisation. Research on reading vocabulary has shown a significant underestimation of the role played by technical vocabulary in specialized texts and lack of information about how technical vocabulary relates to other types of vocabulary. Also in this article has shown a study of the reading vocabulary in an architecture text and the technical vocabulary in an applied linguistics texts.*

Key words: *technical, vocabulary, specialized,terminology,terms ,civil,reading, field.*

АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ РАЗВИТИИ ИНОСТРАННОЙ РЕЧЕВОЙ

ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ

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Аннотация: В данной статье описаны наиболее часто используемые материалы для чтения со специализированными текстами. Цель этого исследования — вызвать дискуссию об изменениях аспектов чтения в связи с революцией в формах общения и представления в результате оцифровки. Исследования лексики для чтения показали значительную недооценку роли технической лексики в специализированных текстах и отсутствие информации о том, как техническая лексика соотносится с другими видами лексики. Также в этой статье показано исследование лексики для чтения в тексте по архитектуре и технической лексики в текстах по прикладной лингвистике.

Ключевые слова: техническая, лексика, специализированная, терминология, термины, гражданско-правовая, чтение, сфера.

چەتئەلنىڭ سۆزلىرىنى تەرەققىي قىلدۇرۇشتىكى ھازىرقى مەسىلىلەر

ئوقۇغۇچىلار پائالىيىتى

ئىزاھ: بۇ ماقالىدە مەخسۇس تېكىستلەر بىلەن ئەڭ كۆپ ئىشلىتىلىدىغان ئوقۇش ماتېرىياللىرى بايان قىلىنغان. بۇ تەتقىقاتنىڭ مەقسىتى رەقەملەشتۈرۈش نەتىجىسىدە ئالاقە ۋە تونۇشتۇرۇش شەكلىدىكى ئىنقىلابقا مۇناسىۋەتلىك ئوقۇش تەرەپلىرىدىكى ئۆزگىرىشلەر ھەققىدە مۇنازىرە قوزغاش. سۆزلۈك لۇغىتىنى ئوقۇش

تەتقىقاتى تېخنىكىلىق سۆزلۈكنىڭ مەخسۇس تېكىستلەردىكى رولىغا ۋە تېخنىكىلىق سۆزلۈكنىڭ باشقا سۆزلۈكلەر بىلەن قانداق مۇناسىۋىتى بارلىقىغا ئائىت ئۇچۇرلارنىڭ كەمچىللىكىنى كۆرسىتىپ بەردى. بۇ ماقالىدە يەنە بىناكارلىق تېكىستىدە ئوقۇشتىكى لۇغەت تەتقىقاتى ۋە قوللىنىشچان تىلشۇناسلىق

تېكىستلەردىكى تېخنىكىلىق سۆزلۈكلەر كۆرسىتىلدى.

ئىچقۇچلۇق سۆزلەر: تېخنىكىلىق ، سۆزلۈك ، مەخسۇس ، ئاتالغۇ ، ئاتالغۇ ، ھەق تەلەپ

، ساھە ، ئوقۇش ، قانۇنى.

The successful development of international relations with foreign countries, the widespread creation of joint ventures with foreign firms, wide contacts in various fields of activity have put forward the task of increasing the requirements for the language training of specialists working in the field of economic, scientific, technical, cultural cooperation, while at the same time being a stable motive and incentive , the need of a specialist in productive cognitive activity.

The language provides an urgent human need for communication and becomes a working tool for researchers, engineers, farmers, cooperators, employees of enterprises that are gaining economic independence. The socially useful activity of a graduate of a school or university, who knows only his native language, is limited by the scope of the functioning of this language. Outside this sphere, he cannot effectively apply his knowledge, as well as replenish it. All this puts forward the need to take into account the changes that are taking place in the sphere of social, national, political and economic relations.

The language is becoming increasingly important in the process of its implementation, in connection with which the question arises of the recipient, to whom it is intended. The task is to improve the quality of language teaching, in the training of humanitarian and technical specialists.

Only a specialist with extensive information can really give the necessary impetus to scientific and technological progress. That is why the question arose of the humanization of technical education, because modern technology also requires

a specialist who is competent in all respects, capable of creatively using all the achievements of science and technology.

Teaching a foreign language is one of the links on the way to overcome this confrontation between two cultures - humanitarian and technical. The humanitarian part of engineering education deepens at the expense of a foreign language. Knowledge of world foreign languages, those spoken by advanced technical thought, has become an urgent need for a specialist of any profile. Instead of narrow professionalism, a technocratic approach to solving technical issues, there is a need for a specialist with a broad outlook of thinking.

The future specialist must obtain the necessary information about what kind of information on the specialty in a foreign language is important in his professional training and realize the role of the language being studied directly in practical activities.

An integral part of preparing such specialists for their production activities is research work, encouraging them to strive for creative search, to master the latest achievements in the field of not only domestic, but mainly foreign science and technology in the specialty chosen by students.

At the same time, it is planned to solve such problems as determining the social order for the training of specialists at various levels and creating information support based on the analysis and generalization of domestic and foreign experience, developing educational and professional models of a specialist for each level of higher education /master, bachelor/.

The level of training of a bachelor in technical universities includes not only natural science training, but also a general humanitarian amount of knowledge on the scientific foundations of a specialty / direction /, including a foreign language.

Obtaining a higher level of education /master/ is also ensured by the creation of more advanced plans and programs for teaching foreign languages, which also include reading texts in a specialty in a foreign language. For this purpose, the

most effective principle is the profiling orientation, which allows selecting texts of a certain subject, which contain the basic concepts of the corresponding specialty.

Teaching a foreign language at a university should be aimed at convincing the student of the need to use knowledge of a foreign language both to raise their cultural level and professionally.

What types of speech activity are needed and which specialists use the most? First of all, you should put reading, in second place - speaking, then listening comprehension, translation, writing. Such are the requests in this area, the social order of the time.

Among other types of speech activity, the mastery of which is necessary for specialists studying a foreign language, reading occupies a special place, being the leading type of speech activity.

What kind of reading does a specialist have to deal with? Among the main leading goals of reading, as practice shows, is acquaintance with publications in the specialty, translation, reading and writing business letters, selection of material for scientific work, compilation of bibliography, analysis of instrument documentation, patent search, etc., study of etiquette in foreign countries of prospective partners, regional studies material.

Knowledge of a foreign language makes it possible to realize such aspects of professional activity as familiarization with sources of information, familiarization with new technologies, as well as mastering the ability to deal with foreign colleagues, firms and enterprises, establish contacts with them, and establish cultural and economic ties.

For the international economic departments of universities, familiarity with international law, international marketing and management, banking terms and abbreviations adopted in international trade is relevant. It is necessary to know the basics of a business conversation, a telephone conversation, the rules of business correspondence, drafting documentation / drafting protocols of intentions, international treaties, contracts /.

Further progress in our economic reforms, the expansion of foreign economic activity, the need to join the world achievements of science, technology, and economics increasingly puts forward the need to organize training in the relevant vocabulary and terminology, which requires a sufficient level of specialist qualifications.

Of the various specific tasks facing specialists in their future work using a foreign language, the task of preparing and conducting practical classes, messages, reports, etc. in a foreign language, using materials in the form of quotations, notes, a brief synopsis, abstract, annotation, documentation.

Opening a specialist access to the leading sources of information - a book, a newspaper, a magazine, reading is one of the main means of satisfying the cognitive needs of a person and carrying out his information activities. It is associated with the processing / translation / of articles from journals, the preparation of annotations and abstracts of original foreign literature in the specialty. At the same time, the goal is to develop in students, future specialists, strong skills in reading literature in their specialty in foreign languages.

Reading is one of the components of the educational process of teaching a foreign language. It is mandatory for every student of the university, where the curriculum provides for a foreign language. The course of instruction in reading should be planned in such a way as to ensure the development of the necessary skills in students as quickly as possible and with the least expenditure of effort. For this purpose, test tasks are also developed to identify knowledge that is subject to control of the material with its use in practical work.

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